

Help and Support

Read instructions/
protection
measures against
COVID-19 and
write an email of
those instructions

Existing Tools

Using these tools in this
scenario makes me feel...

What would help?

Simpler
processes??

Help?

Help and Support

Search on the internet for a specific location to organise a vacation: route, accomodation, restaurants, pharmacies, museums, etc.

Existing Tools

Using these tools in this scenario makes me feel...

What would help?

Simpler processes?

Help?

A platform for booking vacations?

Help and Support

Creation of a
power point (ppt)
presentation
about the
protection
measures against
COVID-19

Existing tools

Using these tools in this
scenario makes me feel...

What would help?

A platform for help
and support videos?

Help?

Help and Support

Organize a week
plan: writing
tasks in a time
manager tool by
date.

Existing tools

Using these tools in this
scenario makes me feel...

What would help?

Integrated
features?

Help?

Simpler
processes?

